

A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education

Dear Readers,

Welcome to the second edition of our **ASAP project newsletter**, where we shine a light on the latest developments and experiences from our journey together.

This issue is particularly exciting as we take you to Porto in Portugal, to share the digital and social media skills we've embraced during our co-creation workshop.

Packed with valuable resources and links, this edition aims to inspire and equip you with the tools and knowledge for a confident and creative digital navigation.

Thank you for embarking on this extraordinary adventure with us.

Enjoy our newsletter and share it with your networks!

Second Co-creation workshop ASAP 2023 in Portugal

Second co-creation workshop in Porto, Portugal, hosted by CICANT, a research institute of LUSOFONA University and ASAP partner, ...

[Explore the gallery and read more here](#)

Co-creation workshops within ASAP project

Within the framework of ASAP project, co-creation workshops serve as point of contact between the project research team and identified priority groups: teachers, educators, families, students, school kids, school directors, experts.

These workshops aim to facilitate moments of connection and shared experiences, they are also helping the project partners to share the outputs and next steps. Participants from different backgrounds and expertise come together to jointly develop solutions, projects, or educational content

[Read more here](#)

The experience of Portuguese school librarians in digital skills education

In Portugal librarian teachers (often referred to as school librarians or teacher-librarians) play a pivotal role in promoting and enhancing digital skill education in schools. During our co-creation workshop in...

[Read more about their role here](#)

ASAP project presented at the ICOLLE conference

CO VLASTNĚ VÍME O DOPADU SOCIÁLNÍCH MÉDIÍ NA NAŠE ŽIVOTY?

Ing. Lucie Brzdková, ProEduca z.s.
 "Projekt byl realizován v rámci projektu financovaného z prostředků Ministerstva školství, mládeže a tělovýchovy ČR prostřednictvím Operačního programu Vzdělávání pro konkurenceschopnost." ASAP - A Systemic Approach to social media and preadolescents through lifelong skills education
 www.asap-project.eu

Hlavním cílem projektu je nabídnout stručný a však podrobný obraz světa preadolescentů a digitálních médií v specifickém kontextu České republiky.

MLADÍ ČEŠI NA SÍŤÍCH

1. TRENDOVÉ SOCIÁLNÍ MÉDIÍ

2. VÝKONNÉ POUŽÍVÁNÍ SOCIÁLNÍCH MÉDIÍ

3. DYNAMIKA POUŽÍVÁNÍ SOCIÁLNÍCH MÉDIÍ V ŠKOLE

4. POUŽÍVÁNÍ SOCIÁLNÍCH MÉDIÍ V KONTAKTĚ S NEVĚDOMÝMI OSOBAMI

5. SOCIÁLNÍ MÍSTO

6. MÍSTO A MÍSTO NA INTERNETU

KYBERŠIKANA VE ŠKOLE

CO MŮŽE UDĚLAT UČITEL?

POSPRÁVA BEZPEČNOSTI VE TŘÍDE

VÝMĚNÍ SÍŤOVÝ VÝKON

SOUDĚNÍ VĚKOVÝCH KATEGORIÍ SOCIÁLNÍCH MEDIÍ

PROJEKT ASAP

METODIK PREVENCE

At ASAP, our commitment to enriching the digital experience of the younger generation takes another progressive stride with the ASAP project. Last September, our dedicated team at ProEduca unveiled an...

[Read more](#)

Digital resources from Portugal

Explore the forefront of digital literacy in Portugal with our latest post, featuring pioneering initiatives from Escolas de Freixo, mochila.com.net, and Oficina dos Media. These platforms embody the spirit of innovation, fostering media literacy and digital skills among students.

[Read more here](#)

You know we have a YouTube channel?

Follow our
YouTube playlist
here

We are on Instagram!

THINK CRITICALLY
BEFORE SHARING
ANY CONTENT
ONLINE!

<https://www.socialmediakids.eu/>

First ASAP
co-creation
workshop

Slovenia
March 2023

Everyday terms used on social media
Alessio, Age 11

Time and Social Media
Lorenzo L., Age 12

SOCIAL MEDIA,
KIDS AND
PARENTS

First ASAP
co-creation
workshop

Slovenia
March 2023

A Systemic Approach
to social media and
pre-adolescents
through thinking
skills education

ASAP goals

LEARNING-TO-LEARN
KEY COMPETENCE

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ASAP?

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ASAP